

Determination of arsenic(III) in nano gram level using Ag-bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone as a new complexing agent

S. Palchoudhury (Mukhopadhyay)

Geology Department, Presidency College, Kolkata-700 073, India

E-mail : palchoudhurysnigdha@gmail.com

Manuscript received 13 January 2010, revised 18 August 2010, accepted 19 August 2010

Abstract : Silver complex of bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (SBTATCH) in methyl isobutyl ketone extract produces reddish brown complex with generated arsine, which is produced on modified Gutzeit apparatus from the test solution when it is treated with conc. HCl and Zn granules. The optimum acidity range is 0.6 to 2 N. λ_{\max} is 465 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the range of 0.6 to 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ at 465 nm. Generated arsine gas in the specified apparatus requires 20 min for complete colour formation. Arsenic can be determined with the Ag-complex in presence of almost all diverse metal ions. The molar absorptivity of method is $0.5 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell sensitivity is $0.016 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The practical detection limit is 3.2 ppb, when arsine from 50 ml test solution is absorbed on 5 ml SBTATCH extract.

Keywords : Arsenic, SBTATCH, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Acute arsenic poisoning is reported¹ in several districts of West Bengal, India and Bangladesh² and this poisoning can arise from ingestion of as little as 100 mg arsenic. Chronic effect can appear from its accumulation in the body at low intake levels for prolonged periods. W.H.O. recommended arsenic level³ in potable water is 10 ppb. The interim-maximum acceptable concentration (IMAC)¹ for arsenic in drinking water is 0.025 mg/L. So eradication of arsenic from potable water and to determine arsenic in nano gram level are the foremost task of the scientific community. There are many sophisticated instrumental methods⁴⁻⁶ for arsenic determination in trace and ultra trace level and among them flow injection analysis system arsenic analyser (FIAS-AAS)^{7,8} may be best, but all sophisticated systems require high expertise as well as supra pure quality acid, reducing agents etc. So easy going and cost effective method is required for day to day analysis, specially in our country, where the poor people are affected much and they reside in the villages⁹. Ag-diethyl-dithiocarbamate is a conventional spectrophotometric reagent¹⁰ and exhaustively used but in this paper we introduce a new reagent which is Ag-bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone or SBTATCH. MIBK extract

of SBTATCH directly absorbs AsH_3 gas, generated in the modified Gurtzeit apparatus. The method is more sensitive, less toxic because of the solvent and less time consuming than the conventional method¹⁰ and it is better than other recently reported spectrophotometric methods¹¹⁻¹³.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of arsine absorbed SBTATCH extract shows its maximum absorbance at 465 nm against an appropriate reagent blank. The complex is stable for more than 8 h.

Acid range : The suitable acidity range for complete evolution and absorption of arsine was 0.6–2 N HCl. Absorbances were measured against series of different acidity and constant range of absorbances at 465 nm were found. The exact acidity range was determined by the titration with standard NaOH solution.

Molar absorptivity, sensitivity, detection limit and optimal concentration range. The molar absorptivity of arsine-silver-bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone complex is $0.5 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 465 nm. According to Sandell's¹⁷ notation the sensitivity of brown colour

arsenic complex is $0.016 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Detection limit is 0.032 ppb where the absorbance of the colour reaction is 0.002. When we utilising the advantage of proportionate solvent extraction the detection limit for water sample would be lower than 0.032 ppb. Optimal concentration range of arsenic is 0.6–8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Accuracy and precision : From identical set of five experiment under optimal conditions the relative mean error and the standard deviation for arsenic(III)-Ag-bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone complex has been determined. These are 0.016 and 0.037% respectively, when arsenic concentration is 5 ppm in five replicates individually.

Effect of foreign ion : Experiments show that it is possible to determine 10 ppm of arsenic(III) reliably within an error $\pm 2\%$ in presence of following ions, V^{IV} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{III} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cu^{II} , Bi^{III} , Pt^{IV} , Os^{VI} , Pd^{II} , Rh^{III} , Au^{III} at 100 fold excess and 10 fold excess of Hg^{II} , five fold excess of Sb^{III} , Sn^{II} , Se^{III} have been tolerated. PO_4^{3-} , CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$, NH_2OH , SO_4^{2-} have no interference up to 100 fold excess.

Estimation of arsenic contaminated drinking water : Five arsenic contaminated drinking water sample which were estimated with flow injection analytical system atomic absorption spectrophotometer, had also been determined with the SBTATCH method and compared. Results have been given on Table 1.

Table 1. Arsenic of drinking water samples analysed by Ag-BTATCH method and FIAS-AAS technique

Sl. no.	Location of source	Ag-BTATCH method ^a (ppb)	FIAS-AAS technique ^a (ppb)
1.	Baruipur (W.B.), shallow tube well	13.0	12.45
2.	Diamond Harbour (W.B.), shallow tube well	11.52	11.15
3.	Howrah (S) (W.B.), Shallow tube well	12.67	12.25
4.	24-Parganas (S) (W.B.), shallow tube well	14.9	15.35
5.	Purbasthalli (zone I) (W.B.), shallow tube well	19.2	19.14

^aEach value is an average of three measurements with RSD < 5%.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss PMQII spectrophotometer was used for the absorbance measurement. Comparative values for arsenic samples were determined by Perkin-Elmer AAnalyst100 atomic absorption spectrometer with FIAS assembly.

Reagent and chemicals : All reagents used were spectroscopic grade and solvents were double distilled. Millipore water was used throughout the experiment.

Arsenic stock solution of 1000 mg/L was prepared by dissolving 1.320 g of As_2O_3 (Merck, Germany) in about 20 ml of 1.0 mol/L NaOH. A volume of 50 ml of 0.5 mol/L HCl was added to this solution and volume was made up to 1000 ml with water.

Silver stock solution of 1000 mg/L was prepared by dissolving 0.390 g of AgNO_3 (E. Merck) in millipore water. The volume was made up to 250 ml. 10% KI solution was used.

Zn granules : 4 g of arsenic free Zn granules were used for each set of experiment.

Pb-acetate : 5 g lead acetate was dissolved in 100 ml water containing 1 ml acetic acid.

Bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BTATCH)¹⁴ : This reagent was prepared from thiophene-2-aldehyde¹⁵ and thiocarbohydrazide¹⁶. Two moles of thiophene-2-aldehyde was added to one mole of thiocarbohydrazide solution in dil. HCl. The condensed bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone was recrystallised from hot ethanol and $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution in spec pure ethanol was used throughout the experiment.

Gutzeit apparatus : Modified Gutzeit's apparatus shown in Fig. 1 was used AsH_3 generation. Ag-bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone-MIBK extract was introduced in the U limb where the AsH_3 was absorbed and produces deep brown colour.

All glass wares were thoroughly cleaned with boiling HNO_3 and de-ionised water. Portions of the apparatus were dried on air oven.

Fig. 1. Modified Gutzeit apparatus for arsenic determination.

Procedures :

Arsine absorbent : Preparation of Ag-bis(thiophene-2-aldehydo)thiocarbohydrazone complex. 5 ml of 100 mg/L AgNO_3 was taken in a separatory funnel and 4 ml of saturated Na-acetate solution was added to it. Then 4 ml of 5×10^{-3} M BTATCH solution was added to the mixture.

Instantly orange yellow complex was formed at room temperature. The complex was extracted thrice with 5 ml portions of methyl isobutyl ketone and volume was made to 25 ml with MIBK. Anhydrous Na_2SO_4 was added to the extract to free it from moisture. This Ag-BTATCH extract was used as arsine absorbent or as the chelating agent for arsenic.

Arsenic estimation : An aliquot containing known amount of arsenic(III) (0–10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was transferred to the clean evolution flask fitted with standard tapered necks (Fig. 1). 3–4 ml conc. HCl was added to each of the flask. 2 ml of 10% KI solution was added. The content of the flask was swirled and allowed to stand for 5 min for the complete reduction of As^{IV} to its As^{III} state. Immediately the H_2S scrubber i.e. the Pb-acetate cotton plugged glass limb was introduced to the evolution flask. To the attached U tube, 5 ml SBTATCH-MIBK extract was introduced from a micro burette. The 4 g of Zn-granules were added to the evolution flask rapidly and all

set up was fixed for complete evolution of AsH_3 gas and for its absorption. The AsH_3 gas generation and its absorption was virtually complete within 15–20 min. The yellow methyl isobutyl ketone extract of SBTATCH was turned reddish brown by absorbing the generated AsH_3 . Absorbance was measured against the appropriate reagent blank.

Calibration curve : Standard solutions of arsenic viz. 0, 0.6, 1, 2, 4, 8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ were used to obtain calibration curve. Samples were analysed and estimated from day to day produced calibration curve. The sensitivity, practical quantitation limit and % standard deviations were determined from the standard curve.

Acknowledgement

Author is thankful to UGC for providing minor research project for the work and also thankful to the Head of the Department of Geology, Presidency College for providing the Lab facility. The author greatly acknowledges her advisor Late Professor S. C. Shome and late Professor A. K. Saha of Presidency College for their initial motivation towards arsenic related work.

References

1. P. L. Smedley and D. G. Kinniburgh, *Applied Geochemistry*, 2002, 17, 517.
2. A. H. Smith, E. O. Lingas and M. Rahman, *Bull. World Organ.*, 2000, 78, 1093.
3. W.H.O. Guideline for Drinking Water Quality, 2nd ed., 1993, 1, 188.
4. J. Dedina and D. L. Isalov, "Hydride Generation Atomic Absorption Spectrometry". John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1995, 182
5. J. Wang, M. J. Tomilson and I. A. Carne, *Analytical Atomic Spectrom.*, 1995, 10, 601.
6. D. Pozebon, V. L. Dresserlu, I. A. Gomesneto and A. J. Curtious, *Talanta*, 1998, 45, 1176.
7. Recommended Analytical condition and General information for FIAS-Atomic Spectroscopy. Perkin-Elmer, GmbH, 1994
8. S. Palchadhury (Mukhopadhyay) and Anima Sen, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, 84, 1148.
9. C. O. Abernathy, R. L. Calderon and W. R. Chappel. (ed.) "Arsenic Exposure and Health effects", Chapman & Hall, London, 1995, p. 92-111.
10. I. G. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, 1987, 734.

11. M. Jamaluddin Ahmed and M. Jobaer Hassan, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.*, 1999, **3**, 9.
12. M. K. Deb, C. Agarwal, K. S. Parel and R. K. Mishra, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1990, **39**, 417.
13. A. Chatterjee, D. Das, B. K. Mandal, T. R. Chowdhury, G. Samanta and D. Chakrabarty, *Analyst*, 1995, **120**, 643.
14. S. Palchaudhury (Mukhopadhyay) and S. C. Shome, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 431.
15. P. C. Guha and S. C. Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 234.
16. W. Weston and R. J. Michels, *Org. Synthesis*, 1963, **4**, 539.
17. E. B. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd ed., Interscience, New York, 1994